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An Assessment of the Effect of Self-efficacy, Reading Culture, Utilization of Library Habits on the Academic Achievements of Student-librarians

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Abstract

The dream of every student on entry any institution of learning is to excel academically and this can be achieved through self-belief facilitated by effective reading which is a complex cognitive process of decoding symbols in order to construct or derive meaning as an essential skill for academic success. Above all, the library should be seen by such student as information warehouse where desired information can be obtained through reading. This study therefore is an assessment of the effect of self-efficacy, reading culture and utilization of library habits on the academic achievement of student-librarians. The study employed a descriptive survey method with a population sample of 250 student-librarians as respondents selected through stratified sampling techniques from five public universities in Nigeria. The study was guided by five objectives and research questions respectively as well as five formulated and tested hypotheses. The principle instrument used in collecting data was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher titled: 'The effect of self-efficacy, reading and utilization of library habits on academic achievement'. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach alpha after being validated by two experts in the field of measurement and evaluation and the reliability coefficient indicated that self-efficacy scale=0.88, reading habits=0.67; library utilization habits=0.90 and academic achievement=0.90. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA). The outcome of the study showed that there was statistical significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement, there exist also a positive relationship between reading habits and academic achievement while the result also indicated no significant relationship between library utilization habits and academic achievement. However the result of this study did reveal that self-efficacy, reading and library utilization habits are effective predictors of academic achievement of student-librarians and by extension, all students.

It was based on the findings that it was recommended that students-librarians should be effectively encouraged, mentored, monitored fortified and persuaded by school management, lecturers and librarians into believing in themselves, reading and utilize the library regularly and that government, university management and university librarians as well as other stakeholders in the management of higher education should ensure that academic libraries are equipped with enough print and e-materials with state-of-the-art facilities as to making the library attractive, functional and conducive, for the students to use among others.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Reading habits, Reading culture, Student-librarians, Library utilization, Academic library

1.0. Introduction

The dream of every student on entry any institution of learning is to excel academically. This is because academic achievement is considered the ultimate barometer with which to measure one's all round capacities and capabilities within the educational sector and in some cases, the society at large. It is through academic achievement that any student can actualize his or her career and potentialities in line with the educational set goals. The drive for high educational achievement among students has therefore mounted a lot of pressure on educational stakeholders as the whole system of education revolves around academic achievement of students. It is against this backdrop that Ajayi and Yusufu (2010) did reveal that improving students' academic achievement is among the basic goals of educational planning in Nigeria.

According to Bhat (2013), academic achievement indicates the knowledge attained and skill developed in the school subjects generally designated by test score. Besides, it includes success students attain at school, college or university; in the class, laboratory, library and or fieldwork. It is noted that academic achievement is being operationalized through students' final grade. Indeed, the issue of students' academic achievement has been one of indent debate in so many media yet it has been shredded in controversy on her to improve academic achievement among educational administrators, lecturers and librarians (Adesulu, 2014).

However, some researchers have examined academic achievement in relation to self-efficacy, reading culture and library utilization habits (Aremu, 2004). Self-efficacy is the belief in one's

capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situations. Self-efficacy is a person's belief in his or her ability to succeed in a particular situation. Bandura described these beliefs as determinants of how people think, behave, and feel (Bandura, 1977). Zimmerman (1995) describes self-efficacy as one's belief in his/her ability to achieve a task. It is imperative to state that self-efficacy might be an important construct to further help the librarians understand the extent to which students can use the library. Self-efficacy beliefs help to determine how one thinks and behaves and in the context of this study, refers to students' belief regarding the ability of the students to use, find and organize information resources for their study and the confidence that they can use information effectively. To this end, self-efficacy is the ability of a student to judge his or her capabilities with regard to task. While Reading stimulates imagination, widens views, expands horizon and helps learning about different people and places and it is important to human development because it is essential in full participation in the modern society.(Onwubiko, 2022), Suffice it to say, that towards the knowledge and literacy society, reading habits are an essential aspect to be considered. Reading is a ticket for success in education and lifetime. According to Onwubiko (2010), reading can be explained as a practice of seeking knowledge information or entertainment through written words. The library on is on part is the information hub of any institution and available information becomes useful only when it gets to the hand of the final user who is a reader as to satisfying the information needs (Onwubiko, 2020).

It is in line with the above assuming role there rose the need for students to be encouraged to cultivate reading habit through the use of library, Iloeje (2014) in a speech titled: 'Restoring reading culture and use of library among young Nigerian adults: Implication for empowering the citizens and Nigerian society' presented at the opening ceremony of the National Conference/Annual General Meeting of Nigerian Library Association posits that every child must be encouraged to read and assisted to become fully competent in reading so that he/she can succeed in school, succeed in life and become a responsible adult citizen adding that students on their part should strive harder to ensuring better performance through the use of the library. This is to say, that reading is a habit that can be acquired, developed and sustained through the provision of necessary infrastructure such as functional library, well planned educational system and parental support. This is because developing reading habit entails a lot of motivation. As

stated by Ibrahim (2014), it is very important to recognize that, parents, teachers and librarians have vital role to play among students to enable them embark on voracious reading and good reading habit while habit on its own is a fundamental part of living. In other words, good habit towards a task may lead students in the right direction based on the axiom 'habit die hard' and to develop good reading habits, students need to be exposed to reading strategies. It is in this area that library comes in because, library fosters the availability of professional librarians who teach students library use which leads to the habit of using the library continually and regularly by the individual with the purpose of meeting his/her intellectual requirement (Erdamar & Demire, 2009) and how to develop good reading habit apart from providing the needed materials for reading. Stating the obvious, it is difficult for any student to develop and sustain reading habit and use of library without due encouragement from either parents, teachers or librarians as well as the student role model and the student's inner curiosity to know the world around (self-efficacy). It is against this backdrop that this study was initiated with a view to assessing the effect of self-efficacy, utilization of library and reading culture on academic achievement of student-librarians.

1.1. Statement of problem

The dream of every student on entry into any institution of learning is to excel academically. This is because academic achievement is considered the ultimate barometer with which to measure one's all round capacities and capabilities within the educational sector and in some cases, the society at large. However in recent time, it is no longer news that the standard of education has fallen to the lowest ebb and this situation has been attributed to many factors which include poor reading culture among students, under-utilization of the library and students not believing in themselves. The belief is that it is the brain behind academic low achievement among students in institutions of higher learning as has been observed in the results of both semester and terminal examinations. This ugly situation has given rise to concern among administrators, concerned individuals, librarians, parents, religious bodies and other stakeholders in education as to the way forward. The question is, could it be master-minded by students' low efficacy as asserted by some stakeholders considering the fact that Tella and Tella (2001) asserted that self-efficacy has significant relationship with academic achievement or as a result of poor reading culture and

poor habit of utilizing the library as indicated by scholars like Gbemi-Ogunleye (2016). More so, available literature shows that this type of study have been restricted to secondary school students so there is need to close this gap. It is in view of this that this study became imperative as assess the effect of self-efficacy, reading culture and library utilization on the academic achievements of student-librarians in Nigeria.

1.2. Research Objectives

The study objective of the study is to assess the effect of self-efficacy, reading habit and use of library habit on the academic achievement of student-librarians in Nigeria. Other objectives include:

- i. To establish the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement of student-librarians;
- ii. To discover the relationship reading habit has with academic achievement of student-librarians
- iii. To ascertain the relationship between use of library habits and academic achievement of student-librarians
- iv. To determine the total effect of self-efficacy, reading and library utilization habits on academic achievement of student-librarians,

1.3. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the correlation between self-efficacy and academic achievement of student-librarians?
- ii. What effect does reading habits has on the academic achievement of student-librarian?
- iii. Does use of library habits has any effect on student-librarians academic achievements?
- iv. Do self-efficacy, reading habits and use of library habits have a collective effect on the academic achievement of student-librarians?

1.4. Hypotheses

The following formulated null hypotheses which acted as further guide to the study was tested:

- H01: There is no significant correlation between self-efficacy and academic achievement of student-librarians.

H02: There is no statistical significant correlation between reading habits and academic achievement of student-librarians.

H03: There is no significant relationship between library utilization habits and academic achievement of student-librarians

H04: There is no significant collective effect of self-efficacy, reading habits and library utilization habits on the academic achievement of student-librarians.

2.0. Literature review

2.1. Conceptual framework

2.1.1. Self-efficacy

According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy refers to one's belief in his or her ability to organize and execute the courses of action required to achieve goals. While Bandura (1982) describes it as the individual's conviction of being able to master specific activities, situations or aspects of his or her own psychological and social functioning. It can be concluded that self-efficacy makes one to believe in his/her capability to overcome obstacle that hinders the achievement o goal.

Academic self-efficacy therefore is one of the important factors influencing academic performance. Academic self-efficacy refers to the students' beliefs and attitudes toward their capabilities to achieve academic success, as well as belief in their ability to fulfill academic tasks and the successful learning of the materials (Meinhardt & Pekrun, 2003 and Chin, Williams, Taylor & Harvey, 2017). Self-efficacy beliefs lead to the individuals' excellent performance through increasing commitment, endeavor, and perseverance (Bandura, 1997). The learners with high levels of self-efficacy attribute their failures to lower attempts rather than lower ability, while those with low self-efficacy attribute their failure to their low abilities (Schunk & Ertmer, 2000). This to say, that self-efficacy can influence the choice of tasks and perseverance while doing them. In other words, students with low self-efficacy are more likely to be afraid of doing their tasks, avoiding, postponing, and give them up soon (Meinhardt & Pekrun, 2003 and Chin, Williams, Taylor & Harvey, 2017).

In contrast, those with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to rely on themselves when faced with complex issues to find a solution to the problem, as well as being patient during the process, making more efforts, and persisting longer to overcome the challenges (Schunk & Ertmer 2000; Pintrich, 2003 and Chin, Williams, Taylor & Harvey, 2017) . This implies that self-efficacy is one of the most important factors in the students' performance. Persons with high self-efficacy, is able to plan effectively and successfully in completion of a task (Bandura, 1982). Such persons believe about their capacities and confidently apply them in such a way that they achieve goals even highly completed tasks. In contrast a person who avoids complicated tasks, unable to plan to achieve goals, and believe in his/her capacities to attain the goals are persons with low self-efficacy. Persons with high self-efficacy are those who understand their capacities and successfully plan their activities while persons with low self-efficacy are unable to perform their assignment (Bandura, 1982).

2.1.2. Reading/Reading habit (Culture)

Reading is the meaningful interpretation of visual or graphical symbols (Nuttal, 1982). Reading is a means of seeking knowledge, information or entertainment through the written words. Reading is said to be a means of language acquisition, communication and sharing information and ideas (Rwanda Book Development Initiative, 2011). Reading is not only the process of interpretation or understanding the text, but an interactive session with the thoughts of the greatest thinkers of the past, present and future genre. It provides an opportunity to transcend into a new journey with own understanding and experience of the subject and promotes new thinking (Rattan, 2013). As explained, reading requires comprehension because comprehension skill helps the learner to understand the meaning of words when alone and in the context of the writer (Drew & Bingham, 2010). This comprehension added Seif (2013) include; skimming, scanning, critical reading and inquiry reading. Reading is one of the most important components of our language and it is an essential tool for lifelong learning for all learners. The reading especially is a resource for continued education, for the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, for gaining information through the media, especially newspapers, books, radio, television, and the computers (Chettri & Rou, 2013). On the other hand, reading habits are well-planned and deliberate pattern of study which has attained a form of consistency on the part of students toward understanding academic subjects and passing at examinations (Owusu-Acheaw & Larson

(2014). The reading habit is an essential and important aspect for crating the literate society in this world. It shapes the personality of an individual and it helps them to develop the proper thinking methods and creating new ideas (Chauhan & Lal, 2012). Reading habit is an active skill based process of constructing meaning and gaining knowledge from oral, visual and written text. Reading habits are the intellectual activities for giving more information, knowledge and learn to various types of things and their activities (Babu & Durgaiyah, 2016). Reading habits also are increasingly important in the contemporary environment of rapid technological change in the global level (Asokan & Dhanavandan, 2013).

2.1.3. Academic achievement

In life everyone wants to be associated with success but failure we know is an orphan. In the educational sector, the academic achievement of students remains the top priority of every school and such achievement is highly celebrated as it depicts that the students have been well educated and parental financial expenses not in vain. According to Aikeen (2000), achievement is the degree of ability already attained while Anastas (2000) describes it as that aspect of measuring the effects of negatively standardized set of experience. The implication is that achievement is a past performance based on learning that has taken place in the past. As recorded by Owitti (2011), many factors contribute to academic achievement and that is why with better performance comes greater reward. In variable academic achievement first depends on a student believing in himself and having the determination to excel academically

2.2. Empirical framework

Inasmuch as the direct effect of self-efficacy on academic achievement is impressive and well documented, it is pertinent to state that the role of self-efficacy as come-in-between has not been properly harnessed in libraries. Indeed noted Zimmerman (2000) and Schunk (2009) self-efficacy can be said to be one of the important factors in the development of academic achievement as students with high self-efficacy join the activities more willingly, work harder and be insistent. Researchers have shown that self-efficacy beliefs affect students' academic successes (Chen, 2009 & Usher, 2009).

Students who are self-efficacious writes Schunk (2013), tend to regulate their learning process and master their academic activities which enhance their aspiration, level of motivation to study more thus increasing their academic achievement. It on this ground that Ormrod (2011) infers that self-efficacy has to do with the ability of individual to measure his competence to complete a particular task and reach his goal. Self-efficacy of a student therefore deals with his/her ability to carry out the class assignments, does the reading regularly, test and examinations in order to be successful in his/her academic pursuance (Laszczyńska & Schwarzer, 2005). As revealed by Klassen, Krawchuk and Rajani (2008), self-efficacy in the academic setting is a strong determinant of performance in all categories of management, teaching and learning. This claim was also corroborated by Faruk-sirin (2011), in his study in which it was discovered that there was a low relationship between academic procrastination and self-efficacy. According to Mbathia (2005), self-efficacy strongly influences our task choice, the level of effort, persistence and resilience as good academic achievement influence not only students' choices in major high schools but also influences their admission into the university as they inspire for more academic achievement. On the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement, Klomegah (2007) in his study discovered that self-efficacy is the strongest predictor of academic achievement. While Bandura (1977) and Carroll & Garavalia (2004) were of the opinion that the beliefs people have about themselves are key factors in determining what they can accomplish irrespective of their abilities. To Tella & Tella (2003), self-efficacy has a significant relationship with academic performance and it is a better predictor of academic achievement. Other researchers whose work has linked self-efficacy to academic achievement include: Pintrich and Degroot(1990); Schunk (1994); Chemers, Hu & Garcia (2001), Duke & Akey (2004) and Ogunmakin & Akomolafe (2013) among others. Hayat, Shateri, Amini, M. et al.(2020) in their study on the Relationships between academic self-efficacy, learning-related emotions, and meta-cognitive learning strategies with academic performance in medical students: A structural equation model found that the students who believed in their abilities and had more positive emotions used more meta-cognitive learning strategies, resulting in better academic performance. For example, Chemers and Garcia found that the students' self-efficacy in the first year of university is a strong predictor of their future performance (Kurbanoglu & Akim, 2010). Alyami et al. (2017) conducted a study on 214 university students and revealed that academic self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on their academic performance . Other studies

have shown that academic self-efficacy has a considerable effect on the students' learning, motivation, and academic performance [Sadi & Uyar, 2013.; Villavicencio & Bernardo, 2013; Ferla, Valcke, Cai, 2009; Putwain, Sander & Larkin, 2013;. Doménech-Betoret, Abellán-Roselló & Gómez-Artiga, 2017). Ahmad and Safaria (2013) discovered in their study that students with high self-efficacy contribute to higher goal than students with low self-efficacy. Students with high self- efficacy believe that they can achieve higher grade on a test of subtraction as compared to research students with low self-efficacy. In other words, students with high self-efficacy believe to solve a greater number of mathematical problems. The other finding suggested that students with high self-efficacy will prefer complex courses than research participants with low self-efficacy. In other words, subjects with high self-efficacy will choose difficult courses of studies in the future.

On the other part, researches have shown that reading assists students and educators expound their knowledge, increase their creativity and enhance their views about life, perception and society belief. Reading therefore is an undeniable mandate that must be carried out by both students and educators as it an imperatively needed by them because of the need to identify students' reading gift as to knowing whether it is normal, average or backward and to further educate the student on better ways to their study habits for improved academic achievement. In view of this, Greene (2011) posits that reading habit is best formed at a young impressionable age in school as once formed, can last one's life time. Reading habit is said to be an essential and important aspect of creating a literate society as it is known to restructure the personality of the students by way of developing adequate thinking method which supports their successful academic achievement in school (Palani, 2012). Other scholars who have conducted researches on reading include among many others, Ogbodo (2002); Bhan & Gupta (2010) and Singh (2011). In as much as their studies were internationally oriented and concentrated on how reading affects the academic achievement of students, they all discovered that reading comprehension skills are vital in attaining academic achievement as it contributes to better learning. Thanuskodi (2011) conducted the study on reading habits among library and information science students of Annamalai University and the result showed that students spend more time, i.e. 11 to 15 hours (77.48 %) reading books and 29.83 percent to surf the Internet. Further, the study indicated that majority of the LIS students (79.53 %) are interested in reading LIS course materials frequently and 30.12% sometimes read LIS related materials on the Internet and recommended that LIS

students need to improve their reading habits.. Bajpai (2013) in his study which investigated, the reading habits of the B-school users like students and faculties revealed that, reading is a tool in the hands of a person by which he/she can increase his/her knowledge to obtain new ideas and reading gets a serious attention among the users.

Likewise, Akanda, Hoq & Hasan (2013) conducted a study on reading habits of students in social sciences and arts: a case study of Rajshahi University. The findings of the study did show that learning leads to an overall mental, professional, and human development. Further, the study also revealed that reading not only gives people, new ideas, information, and insights, it also helps them to become more complete in every aspect. Owusu-Acheaw and Larson (2014) also in their study revealed that that majority of the respondents had the view that reading habits have effect on academic performance and that there is a direct relationship between reading habits and academic performance but laziness is one of the basic hindrances to reading among the respondents.

According to Daniel et al., (2017) in their study on effect of reading habits on the academic performance of students: a case study of the students of Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State., the major factors militating against students reading habit is the Social media, e.g. Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, 2go etc.. The study further revealed that reading habits have significant effect on academic performance of the students. Vellaichamy & Jeyshankar (2014) examined the reading habits of Alagappa University central library users (AUCL) only and found that for majority of users prefer reading at home (36.67%) followed by library (24.67%) and classroom (21.01%). The study indicated that one of the major goals of the university central library is to inspire a love for reading and to promote a reading culture among its users.

Writing on academic achievement, Kizlik (2012) disclosed that it is commonly measured by examination or continuous assessment noting that there is no general agreement on how it is best tested or which aspect is most important for instance procedural knowledge such as skills or declarative knowledge such as facts. Becoming a good student Kizlik (2012) added, requires making a decisive decision through constant and deliberate practice of good reading habit and that for them to attain better academic achievement, they must be encouraged to improve their

reading habit, if not, their desired outcome may not be achieved. This is the main why the development of good reading habit is a combined effort of parents and teachers he concluded.

Furthermore, studies have also revealed that use of library habit has effect on academic achievement of students. According to Dange and Praven (n.d), there is a positive and significant correlation between the academic achievements of secondary school students with their use of library facilities in their schools. However, Okoro (2014) observed that most students do not consider the use of library paramount in their quest for knowledge. While Australian Council for Educational Research (2013) declared that there are evidences to show that among other things, a strong library programme can lead to higher student academic achievement. Among these evidences are; a strong computer network connection from the school library's resources to the class and laboratories has an impact on the students' achievement, a print-rich environment leads to more reading and free voluntary reading is the best predictor of comprehension, vocabulary growth, spelling and grammatical and writing styles and integrating information literacy into the curriculum can improve students' mastery of both content and information seeking skills.

In the words of Ahmad, Malik and Azeem (2014), reading habit, skill and attitude predict academic achievement while Benwari and Nemine (2014) in their study on intensive reading as a study habit and students' academic achievement in economics in selected secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria found that intensive reading, doing of home-works and assignments are among the factors that affect academic achievement of these secondary school students. In his contribution, Furthermore, Jato, Oguniyi and Olubiyo (2014), in their study on study habits, use of library and students' academic performance discovered that irregular use of school libraries by the students was one the factors that lead to their poor scores in test and examinations. Anyadike (2000) also established a relationship between library use and students academic achievement as the outcome shows that students perform better when the regularly use the school library than when they do not, while Gbemi-Ogunleye (2016) in her study on library use and students' academic achievement: Implication for counseling, found that, there is a significant correlation between library use and students' academic achievement.

3.0. Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey method with a population sample of 250 student-librarians as respondents selected through stratified sampling techniques from five public universities in Nigeria (.Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria; Delta State University, Abraka, Imo State University, Owerri, Michael Okpara University Of Agriculture, Umudike and University Of Nigeria Nsukka) with each producing 50 respondents. The study was guided by four objectives and research questions respectively as well as four formulated and tested hypotheses. The principle instrument used in collecting data was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher titled: ‘The effect of self-efficacy, reading and utilization of library habits on academic achievement’ (TESRULNAA). The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach alpha after being validated by two experts in the field of measurement and evaluation and the reliability coefficient indicated that self-efficacy scale=0.88, reading habits=0.67; library utilization habits=0.90 and academic achievement=0.90 The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA).

4.0. Presentation and Analysis of Data

Academic achievement of student-librarians (2018/19 Academic Session)

Code	Courses	A		B		C		D		E		Ranking
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
LIS 213	Technical Services in libraries	48	19.2	72	29	75	30	45	18	10	4	4 th
LIS 222	Oral Tradition & Cultural Literature	75	30	80	32	67	26.8	28	11.2	5	2	3 rd
LIS 241	Introduction to Library Admin	105	42	90	36	25	10	22	8.8	5	2	2 nd
LIS 234	Information Users	105	42	88	35.2	40	16	15	6	2	0.8	1 st

Key: A=Distinction. B=Very Good, C=Good. D=Fair, E=Fail

N=Number of Respondents

Figure 1: Academic Achievement of Student-librarians 2018/19 Academic Session

Table 1 and figure 1 above showed data in respect of student-librarians academic achievement in 4 compulsory courses for 2018/2019 Academic Session in that academic achievement is determined by students' performance in the past. The students were assessed based on four compulsory courses sat for in their 200 level. The data revealed that the highest level of academic achievement was recorded in 'Information Users' with 105 students scoring 'A'. 88 scoring 'B' and 40 scoring 'C' with a failure record of only 2 or 0.8% students, while ;Introduction to Library Administration was ranked 2nd with 105 or representing 42% of the respondents scoring 'A'. 90 or 36% scoring 'B', 10% or 25 respondents had 'C' with a failure % of 2 or 5 respondents. Least ranked was 'Technical Services in Libraries' with a failure rate of 4% representing 10 respondents with only 48 of the respondents or 19.2% scoring 'A'

Table 2: Self-efficacy of student-librarians

Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
I always try to solve difficult problems on my own.	3.47	0.878
I can solve most problems if I put necessary effort	3.36	0.904
I am confident in using different information resources	3.41	0.860
I can easily utilize the library to get information for my assignment	3.35	0.910
It is easy for me to get current and accurate information	3.32	0.873
I can easily handle whatever that comes my way	3.30	0.938
If I have any challenge, I can easily think of a solution	3.26	0.983
I can get myself to study in the case of other distracting things	3.20	0.92
I can plan and organize myself for any academic work	3.12	1.058

I can comfortable arrange a place to study devoid of distraction	3.11	0.97
I can get my needed information using ICT facilities	3.07	1.048
I can always meet the deadline for any academic assignment	3.01	1.13
It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my objectives	2.88	1.080
I can recollect very well every information presented in the course of lectures and reading textbooks	2.60	1.208

Table 2 above contains data on student-librarians' self-efficacy. The data showed that the highest ranked are those who could endeavour to solve difficult problem on their own with a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.47), followed by those who can confidently use different information resources with a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.41). With a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.36) those who can solve most problem if they put necessary effort took the 3rd position. This was closely followed by those who could easily utilize the library to get information for their assignments with a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.35). Taking the rear, were those who can meet deadline for any academic work with a mean score of (\bar{x} =3.01), those who can stick to their aims and accomplish their objectives with a mean score of (\bar{x} =2.88) and the lowest ranked as rated by the respondents were those who can recollect very well every information presented in the course of lectures and reading textbook with a mean score of (\bar{x} =2.6).

Table 3: Reading habits of student-librarians

Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
Reading for examination	4.30	1.12
I enjoy reading	4.11	1.06
Reading for me is a necessity	4.01	1.25
Reading during holidays	3.97	1.21
Reading for information	3.93	1.12
I create time to read	3.93	1.27
I read every day	3.86	1.04
I love to read at my leisure	3.85	1.4
I love reading for pleasure	3.84	1.16
I see reading as a way of life	3.8	1.3
I read for my personal development and growth	3.8	1.3
I read for reading sake	3.74	1.4
I derive joy reading in the bedroom	3.73	1.31
I must read before going to bed	3.73	1.31
I like reading in the school library	3.54	1.44
I can read for two hours or more at a stretch	3.5	1.29
I can read while lying in the bed	3.47	1.36
I read two novels or more within a month	3.45	1.46
I like reading in the classroom	3.35	1.36
I like reading in the living room	3.33	1.40

I read, whenever I feel depressed	2.90	1.5
I read only when am asked to do so	2.86	1.51
I read in the vehicle while travelling	2.75	1.46
I can read up to five hours at a stretch	2.66	1.37
I read only twice in a week	2.60	1.45
I read a book a month	2.6	1.55
I read only once a week	2.52	1.47
I have no cultivated the habit of reading	2.06	1.45
For me, reading is unnecessary	2.05	1.46

The data displayed in table 3 is on the reading habits of the student-librarians. Ranking highest in the reading habit was reading for examination with a mean score of (\bar{x} =4.30), followed by who enjoy reading with a mean score of (\bar{x} =4.11). Those who see reading as a necessity were rated 3rd with a mean score of (\bar{x} =4.01), reading during the holidays (\bar{x} =3.98), those reading for information (\bar{x} =3.93) and creating time to read (\bar{x} =3.93) were ranked 4th and 5th respectively. 2nd to the least in rating were those who have not cultivated reading habit (\bar{x} =2.06) and the lowest being those who felt that reading was unnecessary with a mean score of (\bar{x} =2.05).

Table 4: Library utilization habits of student-librarians

Item	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
I try to utilize all needed library facilities	2.98	1.063
I borrow book from the library	2.81	1.098
I consult the library staff anytime am in need of any information material	2.74	1.092
I always ask a librarian for assistance when the need arises	2.74	1.084
I make use of the library catalogue when searching for a book	2.73	1.085
I glance through the shelve when I want to retrieve materials for my assignment	2.68	1.128
I only go to the library to read my lecture notes	2.68	1.075
I consult the reference materials in the library for my researches	2.64	1.068
I use the library on daily basis	2.56	1.084
I only visit the library to read newspapers	2.21	1.112
I make use of e-resources in the library	2.2	1.066
I visit the library to socialize with friends	2.13	1.138
I only use the library, when I have any assignment	2.00	1.047

The data in Table 4 above houses respondents rating of student-librarians' library utilization habit. As indicated, the highest ranked habit was students trying to utilize all needed library facilities with a mean score of (\bar{x} =2.98), with a mean score of (\bar{x} =2.81) borrowing books from the library ranked 2nd followed by asking the librarians for assistance when the need arises and consulting library staff when in need of information with mean scores (\bar{x} =2.74) respectively

stood at the 3rd position. Visiting the library to social with friends (\bar{x} =2.13) and using the library only when there are assignments (\bar{x} =2/00) were the least rated library utilization habits.

Table 5: correlation between self-efficacy and academic achievement

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	R	Sig.	Remark
Self-efficacy	250	3.18	0.47	0.08	0.05	Significant
Academic achievement	250	3.78	0.78			

The data in table 5 is a summarized Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the correlation coefficient between self-efficacy and academic achievement. The outcome of the test shows that there is a statistical significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between self-efficacy and academic achievement of student-librarians ($r = 0.08$). The implication is that from the data available there is not sufficient evidence to back-up the null hypothesis and for this reason, the null hypothesis (H_01) was rejected. This indicates that self-efficacy significantly correlates with academic achievement of student-librarians positively.

Table 6: Correlation between reading habits and academic achievement

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	R	Sig.	Remark
Reading habits	250	3.37	0.51	0.23	.000	Significant
Academic achievement	250	3.78	0.78			

The result of the PPMC analysis as displayed in table 6 shows that there is a significant correlation between reading habits and academic achievement of student-librarians ($r = 0.23$, $p < 0.05$). It is on this ground that null hypothesis 2 (H_02) was rejected. The implication is that reading habits correlate with academic achievement of student-librarians and this correlation is positively inclined.

Table 7: Correlation between Library utilization habits and academic achievement

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	R	Sig.	Remark
Library use habits	250	32.54	0.65	0.03	.373	Not significant
Academic achievement	250	3.78	0.78			

The data in table 7 is a summary of PPMC analysis of tested null hypothesis 3 (H_03). The outcome shows that there is no statistical significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation between library utilization habits and academic achievement of student-librarians ($r = 0.03$). In this case, there is substantiated evidence that backed-up the proposed null hypothesis it is therefore accepted. This implies that there is relationship between student-librarians academic achievement and their use of library habits.

Table 8: Regression analysis showing total effect of self-efficacy, reading habits, and library utilization habits on academic achievement

R=0.25 R sq=0.060 Adjusted R sq=0.057					
Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	9.709	3	3.236	5.237	.000
Residual	141.804	244	0.581		
Total	150.513	247			

The data in the above table showed the collective effect of self-efficacy, reading habits and library utilization habits on academic achievements of student-librarians. The data revealed that all the predictors (self-efficacy, reading habits & library utilization habits) which are constant and independent variables have collective effect on the academic achievement (dependent variable) of the student-librarians ($r=0.25$). From the adjusted r square the implication is that self-efficacy, reading habits and library utilization habits account for of all round variance in the academic achievement of student-librarians. Besides, using regression analysis variance for further verification the produced ($F_{(1,000)} = 5.237$; $P < 0.05$). To this end, the null hypothesis 4 which states that ‘there is no collective significant effect of self-efficacy, reading habits and library utilization habits on academic achievement of student-librarians’ was rejected.

5.0. Discussion of Results

In the context of this study, the academic achievement of student-librarians were measured based on the courses and their scores as displayed in table 1 and figure 1.. This is in line with the stand of Aiken (2000) who defines achievement as the degree of ability already attained and the assertion of Anastas (2000) that it is the aspect of measuring the effects of negatively standardized sets of experience. This implies that achievement is all about past performance based on past learning. The outcome of this study therefore shows that student-librarians as a result of self-efficacy always try to solve difficult problems on their own; can solve most problems if they put necessary effort; are confident in using different information resources, can easily utilize the library to get information for my assignment, it is easy for them to get current and accurate information, can easily handle whatever that comes their ways and can plan and organize themselves for any academic work among other things (see table 2) and there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance of student-librarians (see table 5). The outcome of this study is in conformity with that of Klomegah (2007) who in his study discovered that self-efficacy is the strongest predictor of academic achievement. The

result is also in tandem with that of Carroll and Garavalia (2004) who did state that the beliefs people have about themselves are key factors of determining what they can accomplish irrespective of their abilities. This result also corroborates the finding of Tella and Tella (2003) in their study that self-efficacy has significant relationship with academic achievement and is a better predictor of academic achievement. Other studies which include Pintrich and Degroot (1990); Hu and Garcia (2001); Greene; Miller, Crowson, Duke and Akey (2004) and Ogumakin and Akomolafe (2013) among others also reported positive relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement.

The study also found that student-librarians have cultivated reading habits in various areas but the highest rated reading habit is reading for examination with a mean score of 4.30 while other 20 items of the 29 items listed for reading habits had a mean score of above 3 points an indication that student-librarians spend quality time reading for various reasons and at different times (see table 3). It was further established based on the null hypothesis 2 tested that there is a significant correlation between reading habits and academic achievement (see table 5). These results therefore corroborate that of Crede and Kuncel (2008) who in their study revealed that reading habits, skills and attitude predict academic performance as well as that of Benwari and Nemine (2014) who noted that intensive reading, doing of home works and assignments as study habits are among the factors that affect academic achievement of students and Parveen (2011) whose finding posits that reading habits are significant variables which contribute to better academic performance of pupils. The implication of this result is that the higher the level of reading exhibited by a student (*ceteris paribus*) on the ground that there is proper understanding of what is read, the better the academic performance.

The study further discovered of the truth that quite a number of student-librarians are of the habit of utilizing the library but the obvious is that the library is not optimally utilized for full academic purposes. As revealed in table 4, all the items listed under library utilization habits had a mean score below 3 points unlike self-efficacy and reading that most of their items had their mean scores above 3 points. This assertion is further buttressed by the outcome of the tested null hypothesis 3 which shows that there was no significant correlation between library utilization habits and academic achievement of the student-librarians (see table 7). This result is in agreement with Jato, Ogunbiyi and Olubiyo (2014) finding in a study on study habits, use of school libraries and students' academic performance, that irregular use of school libraries by

students was one of the factors for poor scores in test and examinations as they noted that the students did not study outside the school yet their academic performance was poor and this assertion may not be unconnected with the perception the students have of the library and the staff attitude as they are of the view that library or no library, they will definitely scale through in their examinations. On the other hand, the result is contrary to the finding of Anyadike (2000) and Gbemi-Ogunleye (2016) who in their separate studies found that there exists significant association between library use and students' academic achievement adding that students perform better when they frequently use the library than when they do not.

The result further revealed that there is a statistical significant ($P < 0.05$) correlation between self-efficacy, reading habits and utilization of library habits on academic achievement of student librarians (see table 8 that showed data of the tested 4th null hypothesis). The implication is that the three independent variables (self-efficacy, reading habits and utilization of library habits) are basic ingredients for academic success of any student when viewed jointly. This outcome supports earlier cited authors like: Klomegah (2007); Ogumakin and Akomolafe (2013), Benwari and Nemine (2014), Jato, Ogunbiyi and Olubiyo (2014), Anyadike (2000) and Gbemi-Ogunleye (2016) who either affirmed that reading habits and self-efficacy have correlation with academic achievement or affirmed that use of library habits have significant association with academic achievement

5.1. Conclusion and Recommendation

The outcome of this study did show that self-efficacy and reading habits are principal factors towards any student academic achievement and that utilization of library habits has no correlation with the student-librarians academic achievement. On the other hand, a look at the three variables as triplet it was discovered that there is a correlation between them and student-librarians' academic achievement. The deduction is that, the negative perception the students have of the library and staff attitude precipitated the under utilization. In a broad sense, the established fact is that self-efficacy is the will in one that makes him or her believe in oneself as to say: 'I can' no matter the situation. This assertion is built on the premise; 'where there is a will, there is a way. Reading on the other hand, expounds knowledge and is also the pivot on which every other academic activity revolves while the library, is the driving access to

knowledge gained through reading which brings out the best in one so as to achieve academically. From the above analysis, the three variables should be treated as triplets co-joined with the purpose of academic achievement with the bulk falling on the library. It is against this backdrop that the following recommendations are made:

- Lecturers in library schools can reduce the students' stress through providing supportive and calm environments since competitive and stressing contexts influence the students' self-efficacy; they can invigorate positive emotions in the students by giving appropriate, positive, and supportive feedbacks, creating interactive approaches in the classrooms, and encouraging the students to cooperate in class discussions instead of competition. Since lecturers' enthusiasm, positive feedback to success, cooperation, sense of belonging to class are positively related to the students' enjoyment of learning and hope for success in learning.
- Staff of academic libraries should work on their attitude because as social workers positive attitude remains their greatest asset. This is because in life it is one's attitude and not his aptitude that takes him/her to the altitude. Academic library management and other stakeholders should know that most librarians in academic libraries only saw librarianship as the last resort and not as a preferred profession. To this end, this set of librarians cannot offer what they do not have and transforming them calls for proper orientation, re-training in the form of seminars, conferences and workshop so as to make them understand the essence of librarianship.
- Most librarians and lecturers in our institutions of higher learning see themselves as lords and masters that must be dreaded by students instead of being role models and mentors. This group of staff scares the students who feel discouraged and work in a state of uncertainty. The bottom line is that librarians and lecturers should be meant to understand that their main role in the first instance is that of a mentor. It behooves them to mentor and encourage every student into believing in themselves.
- The library and librarians should from the day of orientation of new students create the awareness of the need to utilize the library and other available personal services provided for students as to making use of the library very attractive. Furthermore, the library should from time-to-time organize library-week for students as a way of encouraging reading and use of library as well as creating self confidence in the students.

- In this case parents are not left out. As a result of moral decadence in our society, people no longer appreciate the fact that the means justifies the end rather they go for the end justifies the means in that most parents have thrown to the wind morality that some students have learnt as a result of parental upbringing that achievement can be through hook or crook and this has made some students losing self-confidence and not believing in themselves rather following the crook way to academic success. In this regard, the advice is that parents should from childhood start educating their children on the need of believing in themselves and the students on their part should develop that achieving spirit of ‘ I can’ and learn how to set for themselves SMART goals in the course of their academic pursuance and other life endeavours.
- Finally as a student when you hear words like: ‘I can’, ‘Don’t give up’, No going back’ ‘Be focus’ and the likes, it is a call to believe in yourself in the spirit of ‘self-efficacy’. So you are advised to read hard and visit the library frequently for there is the home of knowledge and with it, you will discover your true self.

References

- Adesulu, D (2014, August 11). Mass failure as WAEC releases results. Vanguard. Retrieved from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/08/mass-failure-waec-release-results/>
- Ahmad, H. I., Malik, K., & Azeem, M. (2014). A study of reading habit and computer technology effect on student in Pakistan. *Journal of Education and Literature*, 1(1), 9–19.
- Ahmad, A & Safaria, T (2013). Effects of Self-Efficacy on Students’ Academic Performance. *Journal of Educational, Health and Community Psychology*, 2(1), 22-28
- Ajayi, I.A & Yusufu, M.A (2010). School planning and students’ learning outcomes in South West Nigeria secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Science*, 2(1), 47-53
- Akanda, A. K. M., Hoq, K. M. G., & Hasan, N. (2013). Reading Habit of Students in Social Sciences and Arts: A Case Study of Rajshahi University. *Chinese Librarianship*, (35). 60-71.
- Aliyu, M.B (2013). Delivery of information services in school libraries in the 21st century: Challenges and prospects. In A.O. Issa, K.N. Igwe & C.P. Uzuegbu (Eds). *Provision*

Of library and information services in the era of globalization, pp525-535

- Alyami M, Melyani Z, Al Johani A, Ullah E, Alyami H, Sundram F, et al (2017). The impact of self-esteem, academic self-efficacy and perceived stress on academic performance: a cross-sectional study of Saudi psychology students. *Eur J Educ Sci (EJES)*, 4(3):51–68
- Anyadike, U (2000). *Reading and information gathering*. Owerri, Nigeria: Dims Printing Press
- Australian Council for Educational Research (2013). *Impacts of school libraries on students' achievement*
- Aremu, A.O. (2004). Psychological and sociological determinant of academic achievement of Nigeria adolescents. *Ife psychologia. An international journal of psychology in Africa*, 12(2), 149-161.
- Asokan, L & Dhanavandan, S. (2013). Reading habits of newspapers among engineering professionals: An analytical study. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 3(4), 36-41.
- Babu, M. R. & Durgaiah, P (2016). Reading habits among student teachers in relation to their age, gender and management. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(4), 170-176.
- Bajpai, M. (2013). Reading habit of B-School users: A case study. *Pearl: A Journal of Library and Information Science*, 7(2), 97-102.
- Bandura A (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychol Rev.* 84(2), 191-215.
- Bandura, A. (1982). Self-efficacy mechanism in human agency. *American Psychologist*, 37,122-147
- Bandura A (1997). *Self-Efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. New York: Worth Publisher.
- Benwari, N. N. & Nemine, E. B. (2014). Intensive reading as a study habit and students' academic achievement in economics in selected secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 3(2), 94-99.
- Bhan, K. S., & Gupta, R. (2010) Study Habits and Academic Achievement among the students belonging to scheduled caste and non scheduled caste group. *Journal of Applied Research in Education* 15(1), 1-9
- Bhat, M.A (2013). Academic achievement of secondary school students in relations to self-concept and parental encouragement. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 4(3), 10-30

- Carroll, C.A & Garavalia, L.S (2004). Factors contributing to the academic achievement of pharmacy students: Use of the goal-efficacy framework, *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 68 (4), 1-9
- Chemers, L.L., Hu, I & Garcia, B.F (2001). Academic self-efficacy and first-year college student performance and adjustment. *Journal of Educational Psychology* 93(1), 55-64
- Chen, P (2003). Exploring the accuracy of predictability of the self-efficacy beliefs of 7th grade mathematics students. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 14, 79-92
- Chin E.C., Williams MW, Taylor J.E & Harvey ST (2017). The influence of negative effect on test anxiety and academic performance: an examination of the tripartite model of emotions. *Learn Individual Differ.*, 54:1-8.
- Chettri, K., & Rout, S. K. (2013). Reading habits-an overview. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 14(6), 13-17.
- Daniel, O. C., Esoname, S. R., Chima, O. O. D., & Udoaku, O. S. (2017). Effect of reading habits on the academic performance of students: A case study of the students of Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State. *American Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1, 27-33.
- Doménech-Betoret F, Abellán-Roselló L & Gómez-Artiga A (2017). Self-efficacy, satisfaction, and academic achievement: the mediator role of Students' expectancy-value beliefs. *Front Psychol.*, 8, 1193
- Drew, S & Bingham, R (2010). *The student skill guide*. Gower
- Erdemar, G.K & Demirel, H (2009). The library use habit of student teachers. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2233-2240
- Faruk, Ş. E (2011). Academic Procrastination among undergraduates attending school of physical education and sports: Role of general procrastination, academic motivation and academic self-efficacy. *Educational Research Review*, 6, 447-455
- Ferla J, & Valcke M, Cai Y (2009).. Academic self-efficacy and academic self-concept: Reconsidering structural relationships. *Learn Individual Differ.*, 19(4):499-505
- Greene, B (2011). Testing reading comprehension of theoretical discourse with close. *Journal of research Reading*, 24(1), 32-98
- Green, B. A., Miller, R. B., Crowson, H. M., Duke, B. L., & Akey, K. L. (2004). Predicting high school students' cognitive engagement and achievement: Contributions of classroom perceptions and motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 29, 462-482.
- Gbemi-Ogunleye, P (2016). Library use and students' academic achievement: Implication for

Counseling. Information and Knowledge Management, 6(2), n.p

- Ibrahim, U (2014). Library and information work for young people: A text for students and practitioners in an African setting. Kaduna, Nigeria: University Press
- Iloeje, M.U (2014). Restoring reading culture and use of library among young Nigerian adults: A keynote address at the opening ceremony of the National Conference/AGM of Nigerian Library Association, Enugu, June 24.
- Jato. Oguniyi, & Olubiyo (2014). Study habits, use of school libraries and students academic Performance in selected secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. International Journal of Library and Information Science, 6(4), 57-64
- Kizlik, R.D (2012). ABC of academic success. London: Harper & Co.
- Klassen, R., Krawchuk, L.L & Rajani, S (2008). Academic procrastination of undergraduates: Low self-efficacy to self-regulate predicts higher levels of procrastination. Contemporary Educational Psychology 33(4):915-931
- Klomegah, R. Y (2007) Predictors of academic performance of university students: An application of the goal efficacy model College Student Journal, 41(2), 407-415
- Kurbanoglu, N.I & Akim, A (2010). The relationships between university students' chemistry laboratory anxiety, attitudes, and self-efficacy beliefs. Aust J Teach Educ., 35(8), 4-14
- Luszczynska, A & Schwarzer, R (2005). Social cognitive theory. In M. Conner & P. Norman (Eds) Predicting Health Behavior. Buckingham, England: Open University Press.
- Mbathia, E (2005). Pupils' reading is better in schools with a librarian: Evidence from Slovenia. Journal of Research in Reading, 21(3), 28-31
- Meinhardt J & Pekrun R (2003). Attentional resource allocation to emotional events: an ERP study. Cogn Emot, 17(3):477-500.
- Nuttal, C. (1982). Teaching reading techniques in a foreign language. *HEB Ltd,*
- Ogbodo, R.O (2010). Effective study habits in educational sector: Counseling implications. Edo Journal of Counseling, 3(2), 1-11.
- Ogunmakin & Akomolafe (2013). Academic self-efficacy, Locus of Control and Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Ondo State, Nigeria. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences 4(11), 570-580
- Okoro, C.C (2004). My people are destroyed: The effect of lack of knowledge on academic Performance of Nigerian Children. Owena Journal of Library and Information Science, 1(1), 13-18

- Onwubiko, A (2010, January 19). Nigeria improving reading culture among students: Roles of School heads and teachers. Daily Champion. Retrieved from www.allAfrica.com/stories/201001200713.html
- Onwubiko, E.C (2022), Application of bibliotherapy by school libraries as a tool for enhancement of reading culture and good behaviors among students. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal), 6971. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6971>
- Ormrod, J.E (2011). Educational Psychology: Developing learners (5th ed). Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Pearson/Merrill Prentice Hall
- Owetti, O (2011). School media resource services in Nigeria: The past present and future Prospects. Education Library Journal, 32(2), 32-38
- Palani, K.K (2012). Promoting reading habits and creating literate society. International Reference Research Journal. 3(1,2), 91
- Pintrich P.R (2003). A motivational science perspective on the role of student motivation in learning and teaching contexts. J Educ Psychol, 95(4):667
- Pintrich, P. R & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. Journal of Educational Psychology, 82, 33–40
- Putwain, D.; Sander, P & Larkin D (2013). Academic self-efficacy in study-related skills and behaviours: relations with learning-related emotions and academic success. Br J Educ Psychol. 83(4):633–50.
- Rattan, P. (2013). Inculcation of reading habit in digital era. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(6), 155-161. Retrieved from <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol15-issue4/B01541519.pdf>
- Rwanda Book Development Initiative. (2011). Importance and challenges of reading culture in Rwanda. Retrieved from <https://www.newtimes.co.rw/section/read/83420>
- Schunk, D.H (2013). Self-efficacy for reading and writing: Influence of modeling, Goal setting and self evaluation. Reading and Writing Quarterly, 19(2), 159-172.
- Schunk, D.H (1994). Self regulation of self-efficacy and attribution in academic settings. In D.H Schunk & B.J. Zimmerman (Eds) Self regulation of Learning and Performance: Issues and Educational Applications pp. 75-99, Hillsdale, N.J.: Erlbaum
- Schunk D.H & Ertmer PA (2000). Self-regulation and academic learning: Self-efficacy enhancing interventions. Handbook Self-Regul Elsevier, pp.:631–49.

- Sadi, O & Uyar, M (2013). The relationship between self-efficacy, self-regulated learning strategies and achievement: A path model. *J Baltic Sci Educ.*, 12(1):21–33.
- Seif, A (2013). *Method of learning and study*. Tehran: Agah Publication.
- Singh, Y.G (2011). Academic achievement and study habits of higher secondary students. *International Referred Research Journal*, 3(27), 2
- Tella, A Jr & Tella, A (2003). Self-efficacy and locus of control as predictor of academic achievement among secondary school students in Osun State unity schools. *Oyo Journal of Educational Psychology*, 1(1), 32-41.
- Thanuskodi, S. (2011). Reading habits among library and information science students of Annamalai University: A survey. *Int J Edu Sci*, 3(2), 79-83.
- Usher, E.L (2009). Sources of middle school students' self-efficacy in mathematics: A qualitative investigation, *American Educational Research Journal*, 46(1), 179-196
- Vellaichamy, A. & Jeyshankar, R. (2014). Reading habits of central library users: A case study of Alagappa University, Tamilnadu, India. *Research Journal of Library Sciences*, 2(2), 6-10.
- Villavicencio, F.T & Bernardo, A.B (2013). Negative emotions moderate the relationship between self-efficacy and achievement of Filipino students. *Psychol Stud*, 58(3):225–32.
- Zimmerman, B.J (2000). Self-efficacy: An essential motive to learn. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, 82-91
- Zimmerman, B,J (1995). Self-efficacy and educational development. In A. Bandura (Ed) *Self-efficacy in changing societies*. New York: Cambridge University Press